

NEED TO ACQUIRE DEMOCRATIC COMPETENCY BY TEACHER EDUCATOR IN GLOBAL SCENARIO

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Abstract

Teacher education has been under going transformations over the years and assuming new meanings and dimensions due to changes in socio-cultural and political conditions of the society, particularly in the context of growing emphasis of applying and integrating democratic competencies. Teachers have a great mission to ignite the minds of the young. The ignited minds are the most powerful resource on the earth, above the earth and under the earth. Educators must develop democratic competency for congenial and friendly educational environment in which learners can grow autonomous through the very act and process of learning. The competency areas are interpersonal, pedagogical & psychological, subject content & methodological, organizational and intercultural. The purpose of the initiative is to develop a democratic teaching style by teacher educator which is global demand of the current scenario and also professional development of the teacher educator is based only on democratic competency-based education and training programme.

Introduction

"Tell me and I forget. Show me and I remember. Involve me and I understand"

.....Chinese Proverb

Globalisation has a multi-dimensional impact on the system of education. It has underlined the need for reforms in the teacher education with particular reference to the wider utilisation of democratic competency; giving productivity dimension to the educational system and emphasis on research and development. This would necessitate making skill training as an integral part of the curriculum besides making attitudinal changes so that the teacher educators do not consider it infra-dig to work with hands.

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The 21st century is well known as an age of learning. Teacher as the top most academic and professional person.

Basically, teaching is inherently multivariate, international humane activity. It is not merely transmitting information; it is mutually beneficial interaction between teacher and learner that catalyzes knowledge construction and meaning making. Thus, there must be active involvement of the learners in learning process by involving, utilizing their previous knowledge and experience. Addressing a learner's prior knowledge is an important gradient in constructivism. It is a complex activity because it is expected in this process that somebody learns something (P learns X) since there is wide range of learning X there exists a number of instructional strategies based on different designs. These strategies have been developed by different philosophers, psychologists, educators, instructional designers and among others. The latest innovation in teaching strategies is the concept of democratic competency. There is an urgent need to develop and acquire democratic competency among teacher educators who are ultimately responsible for shaping the destiny of the nation.

Teacher is like a fountain head. If it throws out clean pure water like nectar, the environment around is all fragrance. Teacher education in our country needs considerable revamping especially in the context of fast changing socio-cultural compulsions and various knowledge contours emerging to shape and reshape the process of teaching and learning. Learning needs freedom to think and freedom to imagine. Both have to facilitate by the teacher and the education system. On the basis of this democratic competency, revolutionary change will come in the field of education. The 21st century is about the management of all the

knowledge and information we have generated and the value addition that we can bring to it. In our system of education at secondary level NCERT has framed curriculum with the guidelines of National Curriculum Framework -2005, based on Yashpal Committee Report - Learning without burdening students, children should not be regarded as growing body of knowledge, rather children should develop certain skills observation , concept building & minimize rote learning. There is need to inculcate human values while imparting education and it can be done only through democratic way.

We are today living in the world of explosion. Population explosion, knowledge explosion, need and demand explosion are some of them. Explosion of expectations is also there. Expectation s of society from a teacher is ever growing and the teacher in 21st century is expected to possess the following qualities.

What is Competency?

Competency includes motives, traits, self concept, attitudes and values, content knowledge or cognitive or behavioural skills- any individual characteristics that can be measured or counted reliably and that can be shown to differentiate significantly between superior and average performers or between effective and ineffective performers. (Spencer and spencer, Competence at Work: A Model for superior Performance). In short, competencies are defined as personal characteristics that lead to superior performance. Competency modelling is a first step to identify what it means to be a superior performer with in organisation. In every job, some people perform more effectively than others. Superior performers do their jobs differently and possess different characteristics than average performers do. A good teacher, with meticulous planning, prepares himself for teaching and the student for acquisition of knowledge.

Models

According to Iceberg competency model, which depicts the various levels of competencies, the skill and knowledge form the tip of the iceberg. The underlying elements are less visible, but they largely direct and control overt behaviour. Social role and self-image exist at a conscious level, while traits and motives exist even further below the surface, lying closest to the person's core. The deeper levels of competencies-traits and motives-tend to drive people's long term behaviour and thus, their long term performance.

- **SKILL** - The ability to perform a certain physical or mental task: e.g. a dentist's physical skill to fill a tooth without damaging the nerve.
- **KNOWLEDGE** - The information the person has in specific areas, e.g.

- knowledge of basic accounting principles.
- **SOCIAL ROLE** - The image a person projects to others, "the outer self," e.g. being a leader or a follower. It reflects a person's values- what he or she believes is important to do.
- **SELF IMAGE** - The way person sees himself or herself.
- **TRAITS** - These are relatively enduring characteristics of a person's behaviour, either cognitive or psycho-social, e.g. being a good listener, or being able to recognize patterns across seemingly unrelated elements.
- **MOTIVES** - These are natural and constant thoughts and performances in a particular area (ie achievement, affiliation and power) that drive, direct and select a person's outward behaviour.

The Outward and the Core

The first are relatively easy to develop and acquire; for instance training can be a source of development. However, the last two are the core of one's personality and are more difficult to asses and develop. It is therefore most cost effective to select for these characteristics. Self-image competencies lies somewhere in between. Attitudes and values such as self confidence and self esteem can be changed with training and positive developmental experiences, although with more time and effort.

We can say that competencies determine whether someone is well matched or not with his or her job , The better the match, the more effective and satisfied a person will be in carrying out what the job or roles requires. Now the challenge is to develop a consistent and coherent typology of competence in diversified approaches in the teaching profession. However, one dimensional frame works of competence are inadequate; the

multidimensional frameworks are emerging speedily. Functional and cognitive competencies are increasingly being added to behavioural competencies the teaching profession. When the teachers interact with the children they do so in the manner of a scientist. This technique promotes creativity among the children. The role of teacher is like the proverbial "ladder", it is used by everyone to climb up in life, but the ladder itself stays in its place.

Under the changed scenario, there is impending need for the teachers to inculcate a habit of updating themselves, so as to enable them to meet the day to day challenges in the class room dynamics. The time is ripe now to convince ourselves that teachers will no more restrict themselves as mere transmitter of knowledge, instead will have to act as a facilitator for the young minds to learn, meaningfully and enable themselves to construct their own knowledge, relating well with their environment. In this perspective, let us be clear that children learn better, when they are actively involved in the learning process. The children are able to draw learning situations from their own environment. The strategic change in the classroom process has to

be a gradual shift of pupil- Tr. interaction to pupil - pupil interaction. Here lies the important role of the teachers to prop-up the learners, engaging each child in learning activity. One has to encourage the children to take part in Debate, Quiz and lot of sharing and learning from each other. This is easy to be said than done. Perhaps our teacher educators will have to acquire democratic competency and train the teachers accordingly towards their capacity building in developing and designing/ selecting, learning situations suited to the context of learning needs of children.

There is a saying that love be- gets love. Undoubtedly, teachers will have to care and love the children to develop a better atmosphere of trust and bonding. They will have to have a clear understanding about children, in their social, cultural and political perspectives. We can not assume the desired role, unless we are receptive and able to generate our own knowledge in tune with continuously evolving process. The text-books have to be related with the construction of teaching- learning and personnel experiences. A good teacher will always inspire the children to ask questions giving a fillip to the curiosity and inquisitiveness of children. This will in fact be the launching pad for drawing the young minds towards constructivism, where in they will be able to construct their own knowledge by connecting new ideas to the existing ones on the basis of the activities they are indulged in. Constant engagement of children in various activities helps them in structuring and re- structuring the ideas, which is the basis of democratic way of teaching learning process. Every teacher educator will have to be trained in creating and providing opportunities to the children that they are able to have a sharp observation, ask questions, enquire the nitty- gritties , reflect and create a series of new ideas one after another.

Student often approach teachers with their academic, personal or other career concerns. While as a teacher, all problems can not be addressed, one can lend a sympathetic ear, offer advice or take up the matter with the management to find a solution to the problem. What the student, however looks for is whether his teacher is willing to give him a patient hearing and whether any sound advice is forthcoming. When required, the student would also like to see how far the teacher is willing to go to help him out of a difficult situation. In reality, there is a big chasm between teachers and students. Teachers believe that they can produce a change of behavior, as is defined in the process of learning, after explaining everything about complex concepts. Students, on the other hand, feel that they have not learned enough from their teachers. As a result, there is a kind of "tug of war" between the two parties. The question is which party should be given more treatment, the teachers or the students. Teaching is passion, not a vocation. The single biggest challenge a teacher faces is to keep the interest of the class a live. This can happen only if the teacher uses training aids effectively, teaches imaginatively, injecting the right dose of humour and practical examples, and involves the entire class in the session-answering question should be everybody's prerogative not the prerogative of the chosen few. This involves some hard work, constant updating of one's knowledge through reading the latest literature contained in books, journals and trade magazines, efforts at constant improvement of communication skills and a constant and burning desire to add value to your knowledge and teachings.

Today's children minds are not empty mug. Their minds are full of information. Hence there is a need to identify the information possessed by children as a resource of learning and to convert this information into cognitive

abilities. To make students independent thinkers, teachers must encourage them to construct and reconstruct their concepts and ideas. Constructivist teaching helps children to construct their own concepts resulting in understanding of contents. The first step in constructivist teaching is to understand students existing concepts. Hence teacher must start the teaching on the basis of student's exposure and experiences.

The teaching learning process is like a U-tube filled with content to be converted in the form of learning outcomes. U-tube has three parts:

- (1) Exposure level (E),
- (2) Filter level or teaching support level (T)
- (3) Learning level (L).

In this process, if filter level or teaching support level does not work or is not used, then all contents in the form of information remains mixed and use of the information becomes difficult. Here E and L level are same. With the function of filter level or teaching support level T, the exposure and experiences of the students can be filter into learning outcomes. ($LT > ET$).

For this process of teaching, teaching strategy can having the following steps:

1. Student window
It includes students observations and findings based on previous knowledge and present situation

2. **Teacher Support Window**
It includes identification and enrichment of contents based on General Objectives, Specific objectives of teaching a particular concept and teacher presentation.
3. **Learning Window**
It includes questions based on curiosity, objectivity, creativity and inventiveness of students
4. **Outcome Window**
It includes teacher-taught interaction based on learning outcomes and application of

Moreover, Tare Zamee Per (TZP) movie highlights the facts that teaching needs to be more imaginative and creative. For instance, while teaching shapes and areas, and types of materials, the school building can itself be used as the teaching-learning material. Teaching should not force the student conform to the existing pattern of the world. The students should be made to think out of the box and define their own goals instead of fitting their ideas with the prevailing ones. Curricula and assessment should be flexible and encourage critical thinking on the part of the students so that they become compassionate and sensitive human beings. It is any wonder that our current educational system does not produce Einsteins and Edisons?

For the feasible purposes, teachers should be given more training and knowledge on how to teach in democratic way. Part of the solution is that the teachers should change their perception about their students. Students are no longer "containers to be filled", instead they are curious people with much potential to learn anything new. What is needed today is the cooperation between teachers and students in finding solutions to the problems of teaching

and learning process. Both parties must realize the importance of sharing and exchanging experiences. Teaching must be very interesting by developing democratic competency among teachers that can help the students solve the many problems they face. Teachers can no longer boast of their overt knowledge. Students can be expected to contribute to the understanding of this science. The old saying "a teacher knows better" is no longer applicable. Pedagogical and psychological relationship with learners appeared to be the most important competence area considered necessary in a teacher's work.

It presents the results of an analysis of national legislative documents and local teacher training curricula with respect to teacher competences. The results of the competence analysis show that the strongest emphasis is on the pedagogical and psychological relationship with learners which appearing (i.e. coded) the most often and therefore was considered the most necessary in a teacher's work. However, in line with the project goals more emphasis on teachers' intercultural competence is needed. The overall conclusion of the analysis will be described in the paper as a description of the shared competences that the Joint Pedagogical Studies aims to provide. The aim of the study is twofold. Firstly, the practical aim has been to produce shared description of teacher competences. Secondly, there is an interest in the teacher competences and the descriptions that are nationally or locally produced within framework of teacher's course curriculum. Competence-based education (and teacher education) has been under serious discussion lately. Two aspects seem to be generally included in the definition of competence: the integration of knowledge, skills and attitudes, and a reference to a certain job context or job situation (Baartman, Bastiaens, Kirschner & van der Vleuten, 2007, p. 116). Hence teacher

competences have been often described with sentences such as 'teacher understands (knowledge)...' and 'teacher is willing (attitudes) and able (skills) to...' in connection to teachers work. The analysis also aimed to outline the shared description of teacher competences in the today context. The conceptual and structural tool for the analysis was the teacher competence framework. The psychological relationship with learners appeared to be the most important competence area considered necessary in a teacher's work. Outline of the teacher competences has four competence areas: subject knowledge, knowledge of pedagogy, guiding and supporting learners and an understanding of the social and cultural dimensions of education. Interpersonal competence deals with the ability to perform communicate and interact in teacher's work. With interpersonal competence the teacher understands the 'means of educational communication at school and in the classroom and is willing and able to 'communicate clearly, making skilful use of a variety of media, and interact productively with pupils, individually and collectively. Teacher must provide psychologically-oriented support for children's growth. With pedagogical and psychological competence the teacher understands 'the processes and conditions of education at both a theoretical and a practical level, has a deep knowledge of psychological, social and multicultural aspects' of education and is willing and able to 'motivate students to engage in learning and working tasks, challenge them to do their best and help them accomplish their tasks successfully. Democratic competence is connected with using things cordially and mutually in the teacher's work. With democratic competence the teacher is 'aware of the classroom environment and its mechanisms and is willing and able to 'engage students, parents and colleagues in planning studies by adjusting plans and activities according to the changes in the learning environment. With democratic

competence the teacher is aware of 'the global context of education and is willing and able to 'help pupils acquire democratic social values, distinctive national traditions, global human values.

Recent innovations in Instructional strategies (IS) & design have opened new challenges & opportunities for teacher educator. This innovative instructional strategy is creative oriented and also democratic in nature which is able to solve the problem of the teacher educators. In today's scenario, the most suitable strategy is those which is very much effective and democratically utilize by the teacher. So, in this knowledge economy it is necessary to innovate pedagogies to enrich the classroom experience & to make it memorable & enjoyable. Latest ICT make this quite easy. In this regard, TCS-Education World encourage & inspire teachers to innovate new practices & pedagogies in the form of democratic competency, to make learning joy full & improve learning outcomes through innovative strategies like field trips, out door activities for experiment learning or learning by discovery. In this context, Intel-Teach programme provided contemporary ICT training which has enabled teacher educators and student teacher to integrate technology into their lessons, and promote problem solving, critical thinking, and collaboration in their classrooms. Above all, now it is essential for teachers learn the art of reinforcement, acknowledging the progress of the learner and praising them, to assure them that they are learning and doing well, and as a teacher he is accepting that the desired learning is the taking place. Professional development of teacher is depending upon this new emerging innovative democratic competency concept. The main purpose is to determine the logic and advantages behind acquiring democratic competency by teacher educator. If the teacher use democratic competency, it will make our classroom more enjoyable and vibrant.

There are various innovative instructional strategies, which is effectively using in democratic way to improve and maintain the teaching-learning quality. These are as follows:

- Cooperative Learning (CL) - Some well known methods of cooperative learning (CL) are Group Investigation (GI), Learning Together (LT), Reciprocal Teaching of Reading (RTR), Cooperative Integrated Reading & Composition (CIRC), Jigsaw I & II, constructive controversy (CC) / structured academic controversy (SAC), student Teams - Achievement Divisions (STAD) & Teams - Games Tournament (TGT). Thus, it helps the teacher in achieving thousands of goals of education because they incorporate intellectual, social & psychological aspects of education & develop interpersonal relationship among learners.
- Blended Learning
- Project Based Learning
- Case Study - Its strength is:
 - Relies on learning by analysis & discussions.
 - Help students in decision making skills
 - Participants to learners to present their ideas clearly
 - Allow learning of social skills
- Simulated Teaching
- Concept mapping
- Peer Learning
- E-Learning
- Tutorials
- In Circle Time
- Team Teaching

Once the teacher is ready develop and acquire democratic competency then he will be able to create appropriate environment to attain all kinds of learning in the classroom and he will change the environment from teacher centered to learner centered. The dimensions on which the changes will take place are given below-

Lower level objective --- Higher level of objectives
Monologue --- Dialogue --- Interaction between the groups
Teacher centered --- Student centered
Content Knowledge --- Syntactic Knowledge
Knowledge as a product --- Knowledge as a process
Convergent thinking --- Divergent Thinking
Memorization --- Mastery Learning

Conclusion

The influence of market economics, the proliferation of technology, and the emergence of new democracies characterize global arena at the dawn of the 21st century. Democratic competencies are required to address the opportunities and challenges of our rapidly changing international educational environment. Democratic competency are necessary to practice of effective teaching and determine the appropriate blend of pedagogical methods by which theories and competencies can be taught and learned best.

Thus we can say that democratic competency determine whether someone is well matched or not with his or her job. The better the match, the more effective and satisfied a person will be in carrying out what the job or role requires. Now the challenge is to develop a consistent and coherent typology of competence in diversified approaches in the profession. However, as one-dimensional frameworks of competence are inadequate, the multi-dimensional frameworks are emerging speedily. Functional and cognitive competencies are very much important for teaching-learning process. Lastly, teaching is a passion, not a vocation. The single highest challenge is teacher faces is to keep the interest of the class a live. This can happen only if the teacher uses always innovative instructional strategies of teaching-learning like imagination, injecting the right

dose of humor & practical example and involve the entire class in the session-answering questions should be every body's prerogative not the prerogative of the chosen few. This involve hard work, constant updating Instructional strategies (IS) through innovation, communication skill, & constant & burning desire to add & deliver value to your Instructional strategies (IS) & design. So, it is necessary to innovate pedagogies to enrich the classroom experience. By fusing above instructional strategies with teaching, teacher can decorates their learner's experience to make it meaningful, memorable and enjoyable. Latest ICT make this quite easy. Teacher can make an education system which will retain the smiles on the faces of our children and it can happen only by acquiring democratic competency.

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When learning is purposeful,
creativity blossoms,
When creativity blossoms,
thinking emanates,
When thinking emanates,
knowledge is fully lit,
When knowledge is fully lit,
economy flourishes